

Functional Chicken Meat

S. Sahu, K. Sethy*, S. Pattanaik, S. Sahoo, P. Nayak

Department of Animal Nutrition, C.V.Sc and AH, Odisha University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, 751003, Odisha

Introduction

Poultry production of last three decades in India has completed its journey from a small-scale business to a rapidly growing industry. Presently this industry has appeared as the most dynamic and fastest growing sector in rural and urban market in India. The productivity of broiler chickens has also dramatically advanced due to collateral progress in rearing method, nutrition, genetics, disease prevention, medication and biosecurity that result gaining optimum slaughter age and pre-harvest losses. The present society is very much concerned about the qualitative characteristic of meat as well as safe products as per consumer demand. The chicken meat has already gained a healthy image. These products are also being designed to perform a particular function or set of functions effectively and reliably, to suit the purposes and the attitudes of consumers. With the self-sufficiency and adequate level of quantitative chicken meat production, change in life style, public demand for meat of specific quality and purpose, the concept of functional chicken meat has more emphasized in developed and under developed countries. Improving consumer's health and nutritional status by altering the nutritional profile of poultry meat through different approaches not only promotes beneficial health effect in consumers but also improves long term market prospects.

Definition

A functional meat refers to a food which on consumption provides a health benefit effect as well as improves the immune system of body to prevent any infection/ disease by augmenting new ingredients or replacing the pre-existing ingredients present in that food. In simple meaning this will be designed in such a way that it provides health promotive effect other than its customary nutritive value. For production of functional meat, its components either added or removed or modified that it improves health status and well-being of consumers or reduction of risk of diseases. The synonyms of functional meat are known as designer meat, fortified meat and healthy meat. Three important basic criteria are very much essential for declaring that meat is functional

one is it is always from natural origin, consumed as daily routine diet and regulating specific process in the body by delaying senescence process, counteracting any infection or diseases and improving the body defense system. So functional meat can be generated in two ways

- Pre slaughter value addition i.e., value addition prior the finished product is generated.
- Post slaughter value addition i.e., value addition afterwards the product is generated.

Purpose of development of functional chicken meat

At the present scenario, consumers are not only aware and but also more conscious about the relationship between their health and the food that they are consumed. More specifically they show more interest towards animal products like milk, meat, egg etc. Among that chicken meat occupies a specific place in human diet as it is a reliable source of superior quality of animal protein with an affordable price for all types of consumers. Apart this, chicken meat is a rich source of niacin, pyridoxin, phosphorus, choline, tryptophan etc. Primarily consumers more concern about the safe and healthy food i.e., free from antibiotics, insecticides, pesticide, harmful microorganisms *etc.* Then they show more engross towards the chicken meat which having reduced substances that are responsible for development of several life style diseases like high blood pressure, diabetes, atherosclerosis, fatty liver disease, cardiac problems etc. At last, now consumers are expected to get some additional benefit from the meat which improves health status by impacting positive effect on physiological processes.

Advantages of functional chicken meat

- Provides a particular function while consuming.
- Provide additional nutrient and non-nutrient benefits.
- They act as anti-carcinogenic, anti-diabetic, anti-hypertensive.
- Cardio-protective, lowering cholesterol level and immune modulating properties
- Promote overall health of consumers.
- Consumer oriented food.
- Free from toxin, harmful substances, pathogenic microorganisms.

1. Pre slaughter intervention

Omega 3 fatty acid enrichment

When polyunsaturated fatty acids contain double bond, three atoms away from the terminal CH₃ group they are called Omega- 3 fatty acids. Examples of omega-3 fatty acids are eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), alpha linoleic acid (ALA), docosahexaenoic acid (DHA), docosapentanoic acid (DPA). These are coming under essential fatty acids as it acts as a constituent of plasma membrane of cell, vehicle for cholesterol transport, lipoprotein synthesis, avoiding of fatty liver syndrome etc. It exerts positive immunological and neurological effects and helps to

prevent cardiac arrhythmia, neoplastic condition, geriatric problems, depression, and altering the blood lipid profile and blood clotting mechanism. Also, it reduces the risks associated with cardiovascular disease by decreasing the serum triglycerides and increased serum thromboxane level.

Fish oil, linseed or flaxseed oil, rape seed or canola oil, marine algae, sunflower oil, soyabean oil, millets etc are rich source of omega 3 fatty acids. Feeding of linseed oil to broilers increases the omega 3 PUFA at tissue level in their meat. Research shows that when we provide diet supplemented with 4 percent fish oil for thirty-eight days in broilers then the all forms of omega 3 fatty acid like EPA, DPA, DHA were found to be positive increment by 5.65, 6.75 and 23.2 times respectively in broiler thigh muscles. Dietary supplementation of broilers with linseed oil and rape seed oil enhances linoleic acid content which will be utilised to synthesize omega 3 fatty acids in future. Fish oil in the diet at the rate of 1.5 % as a source of n-3 fatty acid was beneficial. Broilers fed with fish and cod liver oil has statistically higher EPA and DHA level in thigh meat than broilers fed with other conventional vegetable oil. The abdominal fat content of the bird reduced with feeding of 10% of pumpkin seed which is abundant in linoleic and alpha linoleic acid (Schneiderova *et al.*, 2007). The effect of these oil can alter the FA composition, n-6 and n-3 FA ratio and improves oxidation stability (reducing the malonaldehyde level that act like oxidative stress marker).

Conjugated linoleic acids enrichment

The CLA refers to a mixture of positional and geometric isomers of linoleic acid (C-9, C-12, C18:2) with two conjugated double bonds at various carbon positions in the fatty acid chain. Numerous health beneficial effects have been attributed to CLA in experiments that ameliorating carcinogenesis, atherosclerosis, onset of diabetes and body fat mass or obesity. Apart of this, it protects immune system and contributes the bone formation and body composition. A significant effect of adding CLA to broiler diets on FA composition of their meat is observed. Linoleic acid concentration increases in muscle and adipose tissue in that case. Decrease in body fat observed by 16% and 14% while providing of 2% and 3% CLA in diet for five weeks respectively in broilers. Dietary supply of CLA for twelve weeks in 27-week-old white leghorn caused decreased lipid oxidation in raw chicken meat. Feeding of conjugated linolenic acid to broilers increases the n-3 PUFA content from 86 to 283 mg/100g of breast meat.

Vitamin-E or alpha tocopherol enrichment

The antioxidants are often included to the diet in order to avoid the occurrence of deteriorated sensory traits. Natural antioxidant vitamin E or alfa tocopherol delay lipid oxidation (reduced concentration of malonaldehyde) and increase phagocytic activity in the immune system as a result shelf life of poultry and poultry product are improved. As compare to breast meat thigh meat is more susceptible to lipid oxidation. Tissues like muscle, liver, adipose tissue etc contain higher amount of tocopherol with increase in concentration of vitamin-E in their diet. By maintaining integrity of cellular membrane, reducing the leakage of sarcoplasmic components from muscle cells Vitamin-E prevent drip loss in meat. Vitamin-E supplementation causes faster degradation of troponin-T results better tenderisation and lower shear force during cutting.

Vitamin-E inactivates phospholipase A₂ that inhibit Ca leakage into sarcoplasm and causes very low Ca concentration in sarcoplasm. That Low Ca content in sarcoplasm brings about the process of pH change and protein denaturation in slower rate so that water holding capacity is increased, lowers water loss and enhanced emulgation properties. 200-400 mg/kg diet of vitamin-E is recommended in the diet for functional chicken meat production. Tocopherol at the rate 7mg/kg of poultry meat are suggested to extend the keeping quality of that meat. Decrease of lipid peroxidation in meat stored at 4-20⁰C is encountered when both vitamin-E and Selenium are added to it (Sahoo and Jena, 2014). Fishy flavour (due to fish meal supplementation) and warmed-over flavour (due to refrigerated cooked meat and raw frozen meat) is reduced by addition of Vitamin-E. Feeding of vitamin-E supplemented diets (10 to 20 ppm) showed significantly lower level of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) in the meat measured after 5 and 10 days of storage.

Selenium enrichment

Selenium is one of the micro mineral that plays some important role in the body by either interfering in biochemical reaction or improving the immunizing power of the body. Being a constituent of seleno-protein, selenium participates in antioxidant defence mechanism, relieving from inflammation, thyroxin production, nucleic acid synthesis, fertility, reproduction and destroying neoplastic cells. Therefore, appropriate quantity of selenium is necessary for optimum body function. Supply of Se enriched food is one efficient way to overcome the Se deficiency. Dietary manipulation of the diet with organic selenium has been observed as one of the successful strategies to increase Se in food. Research proved that dietary supplementation of the hen s diet with a higher amount of Se resulted in increased glutathione activity in the hen's blood, as well as

an increase Se deposition in meat of that hen. Organic Se enriched chicken meat remain fresh for a longer period of storage. Se enriched yeast (organic selenium), harvested by inoculating *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* culture in media rich with selenium.

0.1-0.3 ppm organic Se per kg diet is recommended for production of functional chicken meat. Feeding of Se enriched yeast increases Se content by 1.59 times and 1.66 times in breast muscle and thigh muscle respectively. Highest selenium retention in carcass of broilers was achieved by supplementation of nano selenium followed by organic sources at 0.1mg/kg compared to sodium selenite. When 0.50 ppm inorganic and organic Se are added to frozen meat causes retardation of the oxidation process during 1st 30 days of the storage. In Korea, selen chicken has been developed as a premium chicken brand with high content of Se.

Lean meat production

Now a days consumer prefers chicken meat with reduced fat with an affordable price for health point of view. In order to achieve this goal, there is an opportunity to alter the composition of diet which includes the protein to energy ratio of feed. Dietary manipulation that may be done by supplementing chromium in diet or branched chain amino acid in the diet to alter myo-protein synthesis. Chromium potentiates the action of insulin and prompting the insulin sensitive cells readily for uptake of glucose. It utilises the blood glucose for the production of ATP resulting lowered fat deposition in the body.

An improvement in carcass quality is observed when chromium enriched yeast at the rate of 1g/kg diet is provided to broilers. On the other side a significant reduction in carcass fat level is observed when chromium picolinate is included at 0.5 ppm level. Organic Cr had increased weight of pectoral muscle meat had less fat and cholesterol content. Chromium supplementation at the rate of 0.2 ppm resulted protein accumulation and fat depletion (Bhat and Bhat, 2011). An increase in lysine level in pre starter diet and methionine level in finisher diets will yield lean breast meat in broiler. Birds receiving diets conjugated with fish oil developed significantly smaller abdominal fat pads than birds receiving the linseed oil treatment.

Reducing cholesterol content in meat

Cholesterol is the class of lipid which is essential for cell membrane synthesis. Cholesterol is of two types i.e. low density lipoprotein(LDL) or bad cholesterol as it acts as vehicle for cholesterol and deposits in the arterial wall and causing firm and narrow another is high density lipoprotein(HDL) or good cholesterol that takes up extra cholesterol and returned back to liver. High cholesterol causes atherosclerosis, high blood pressure, obesity, cardiac disease etc. several

studies show that micro minerals like copper, chromium, zinc, vanadium, iodine and vitamins like vitamin-A, C, niacin reduces cholesterol level. Feeding of dehydrated alfa alfa to broilers contain saponin which is hypocholesterolemia in nature that reduces cholesterol in their meat. Glycine, lysine, methionine, tryptophan is when supplemented in the diet it reduces cholesterol content. Broilers fed *Lactobacillus* culture show decrease in serum cholesterol. Supplementation of Cu (35-126 mg/kg feed) increases the oleic acid and reduced meat cholesterol. A significant reduction (10-25%) in meat cholesterol level seen when birds are fed with herbal supplementation like basil/tulsi, bay leaves, garlic, citrus pulp, grape seed pulp, spirulina, tomato pomace (lycopene). Probiotics together (*Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *L. casei*, *B. bifidum*, *A. oryzae*, *S. faecium* and *Toluropsis*) @ 100 ppm in diet improved moisture, protein, ash and reduced cholesterol content in leg and breast meat of chicken (Peric *et al.*, 2011). Canola oil, linseed oil, soyabean oil, sunflower oil reduces cholesterol content in Cockrel thigh and breast meat.

Enrichment with carotenoids

Carotenoids are the organic pigment that is found in the chloroplast and chromoplast of plant and some other photosynthetic organism like algae, some bacteria and fungi. People consuming the carotenoid rich food have healthier and lower mortality from number of chronic illnesses. Good source of is

Lycopene- Tomato, Watermelon, grapefruit

Alpha carotene- Carrots, Spinach, Pumpkin, Sweet potato, Apple, Green bean, Kale etc

Beta carotene- sweet potato, Kale, Carrot, Turnip green, spinach.

Beta cryptoxanthine- Papaya, Mango, Peaches, Orange, Bell peppers, Watermelon.

Lutein and Zeaxanthine- Turnip green, broccoli, Corn, Lettuce, Spinach.

2. Post slaughter intervention

Feed ingredients	Source	Benefits
Dietary fibre	Oat bran, wheat, maize flour, pea starch, lupin, fruits (like orange, apple) vegetables (beet, pea)	Improves yield, texture, thermal gelatinization, emulsifying properties, reduces gastro intestinal disorder, act as non-calorific bulking agent
Inulin	Chicory, Garlic, Onion	Relieve from constipation, reduces meat cholesterol, promotes weight loss, controls diabetes, improved mineral absorption and bone health, prevent Colon cancer

Amino acids, peptides, proteins	Soyabean, Sunflower, cow pea, linseed	Act as structural protein, Health promoting properties against cardiovascular disease, cancer and osteoporosis
Choline	Sunflower, lecithin syrup, spinach, cauliflower	Act as phospholipid precursor, acetyl choline synthesis, regulate mood, memory, muscle control and other function
PUFA	Fish oil, walnut, corn oil, flax seed and flax oil, sesame seeds, sunflower oil	Regulate blood pressure and glucose level, regulate nervous function, blood clotting, improves muscle strength
Herbal	Tulsi, basil, curry leaves, rosmary, turmeric, garcinia, black pepper, nutmeg	Source of antioxidants, promotes heart health and immune system, low in cholesterol, act as growth promoter in broiler
Probiotics	<i>Lactobacillus</i> , <i>Bifidobacterium</i>	Improves intestinal microbial balance, prevent diseases like IBD, colon cancer, <i>Helicobacter pylori</i> infection, allergies
Vitamins and minerals	Ca, Se, Fe, Cu, Vitamin-E, Ascorbic acid, carotene	Regulate normal body physiology and metabolism, act as antioxidant, reduce cholesterol content.

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